

International Workshop

"Green and Blue Deals: Planetary Mountains and Oceans"

Hybrid – online & in-person

November 14, 2024, Harvard, UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

Registration of the participants	08.00-08.30
Event welcome	08.30-08.45
Plenary speakers	08.45-11.00
<i>BRINDUSA STERPU, Centre for Mountain Economy & CBM International University</i> Blue Deals for a Sustainable Future: Preserving Planetary Mountains and Oceans through Integrated Conservation, Climate Action, and Cross-Border Environmental Stewardship	08.45-09.15
<i>MIHAI COVACI, Hyperion University & CBM International University</i> Green Deals for Global Conservation: Protecting Planetary Mountains and Oceans through Sustainable Policies and Ecosystem Restoration	09.15-10.45
Q & A	10.45-11.00
Parallel sessions	11.00-12.00
<i>Session 1 – Green Deals: Protecting Mountains and Oceans</i> <i>EVA CLARK, Akademos Learning UK</i> Green Deals: Advancing Sustainable Solutions for the Protection and Preservation of Mountains and Oceans	11.00-11.30
<i>ALBERT LEWIS, 9462-9755 Quebec Canada</i> Green Deals: Driving Sustainable Policies and Innovative Solutions for the Protection and Long-Term Preservation of Mountains and Oceans	11.30-12.00

<p><i>Session 2 – Blue Deals: Preserving Mountains and Oceans</i></p> <p><i>JACK BAILEY, Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences</i></p> <p><i>Austria</i></p> <p><i>Blue Deals: Promoting Global Sustainability through Integrated Strategies for the Conservation and Protection of Mountains and Oceans</i></p> <p><i>OLIVIA CAMPBELL, Zealandina Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Blue Deals: Advancing Global Sustainability through Collaborative Strategies and Innovative Approaches for the Preservation and Protection of Mountain and Ocean Ecosystems</i></p>	<p>11.00-11.30</p> <p>11.30-12.00</p>
<p>Coffee break</p>	<p>12.00-12.15</p>
<p><i>Session 1 – Green Deals: Protecting Mountains and Oceans</i></p> <p><i>CARLA SELMA, Akademos Agency UK</i></p> <p><i>Green Deals: Fostering Global Sustainability through Innovative Policies, Collaborative Approaches, and Strategic Solutions for the Conservation of Mountains and Oceans</i></p> <p><i>PARVATI AARAV, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Green Deals: Advancing Global Sustainability through Innovative Policy Frameworks, Collaborative Efforts, and Strategic Initiatives for the Protection of Mountains and Oceans</i></p>	<p>12.15-12.45</p> <p>12.45-13.15</p>
<p><i>Session 2 – Blue Deals: Preserving Mountains and Oceans</i></p> <p><i>LASHMI DURGA, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Blue Deals: Driving Global Sustainability through Collaborative Solutions and Innovative Strategies for the Conservation and Resilience of Mountain and Ocean Ecosystems</i></p> <p><i>SHI CHEN, CBM International University</i></p> <p><i>Blue Deals: Shaping Global Sustainability through Strategic Collaboration and Innovative Approaches to Safeguard and Enhance Mountain and Ocean Ecosystems</i></p>	<p>12.15-12.45</p> <p>12.45-13.15</p>
<p>Q&A</p>	<p>13.15-13.45</p>

CBM International University USA

Akados Learning UK

9462-9755 Quebec CA & AT (Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences)

Concluding remarks	13.45-14.00
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Location: Cambridge - Harvard Square-Mifflin Place, Harvard Square, Cambridge,
02138, United States of America